

Virtual Try on using Augmented Reality & Machine Learning

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Abstract: *With the advanced technology growth, online shopping as known as e-shopping has grown exponentially throughout the world nowadays. Advances in e-shopping has driven shopping revolution where customers are able to purchase items anywhere and anytime. Despite the benefits of e-shopping, the main drawback is the difficulty for online shoppers to try items on especially for clothing. Hence, a virtual fitting room using AR is proposed to be developed as a mobile application to allow shoppers to visualize how clothing looks and fits on their bodies without wearing it actually. This is to improve shoppers' shopping experience by giving them an ability to virtually try clothing on in order to check for size, fit or style. In this development, AR, human body detection and motion tracking are integrated to fit the model of garment to user's body in real-time by tracking user's body movements through the web camera. The body skeleton-joint positions are recognized, detected and tracked using pose estimation model. In addition, the body and garment measurements are also analysed and interpreted to help in seamlessly fitting the virtual garments to the body.*

Keywords: *Augmented reality, Graphical User Interface, AR virtual fitting room, Garment Model*

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advanced technology growth, online shopping as known as e-shopping has grown exponentially throughout the world nowadays. Advances in e-shopping has driven a shopping revolution where customers are able to purchase items anywhere and anytime. Despite the benefits of e-shopping, there are some disadvantages which deter customers from purchasing items online. Most of the them wish to check whether the clothing fits in size as sometimes the purchased clothing does not match with the size description provided by the seller. Offering return polices or free shipping for returns is aim to compensate for inadequate fit and sizing content but it will bring much inconvenience to the seller. In fact, customers will choose one or both clothing shopping styles which are online shopping and in-store shopping based on their specific demands. However, both the ways are unable to achieve a goal which is allowing customers to check for size, fit or style of their favorited clothing without physically trying it on body. Therefore, an AR virtual fitting room is proposed in this project in order to help customers to accomplish their shopping goals. Augmented reality (AR) is a technology that delivers an enhanced view of real-world by superimposing computer-generated information such as graphics over the real objects and surroundings. The superimposed information can either add something to real-world as known as constructive AR or mask real-world as known as destructive AR. In AR-based environment, the virtual and physical information surrounding user's current location becomes interactive and digitally manipulated. Users can experience a new and enhanced version of natural world where the superimposed information aids users' daily activities. AR applications have been applied to various types of industries such as entertainment, retail, education, medicine etc. For example, Snapchat provides fancy filters for users to apply them over faces to take a picture using AR. The completed picture is then becoming the combination of real image with overlaid elements. Moreover, retail industry can benefit from AR technology by offering customers to try things on before placing any order at no cost of time or resources. One of the successfully cases is IKEA Place AR application which enables customers to preview and try out furniture items at home before buying it. Other than that, in order to improve immersion of users into AR, human body detection is also integrated with AR technology to produce an application which allows users to interact and control the virtual element through body movements.

Figure .1 Samsung Galaxy S10's AR Emoji is an AR mobile application

According to figure 1.1 Samsung Galaxy S10's AR Emoji is an AR mobile application that utilizes both human body recognition and AR technologies. The personalized 3D avatar model which is blended with the real-world environment moves like the user. This is done by capturing the specific points of the user's body and then tracking the body movements. In addition, with the help of human body scanning technology, accurate body measurements can be obtained for further analysis. The body measurements data can be utilized to help users find clothes that fit them perfectly.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Zeekit, a fashion tech start-up has developed the first virtual fitting room application which offers an interactive and different shopping experience for every person. It allows online shoppers to see themselves in any piece of garment found on-line without having to physically try it on by using their real photo and body measurements. Using real-time image processing technology, Zeekit maps a person's image into thousands of segments by using its patented technology which involves rendering 3D maps over a 2D images (Doupnik, 2016). According to Alvarez (2017), the application enables shoppers to try on virtual garments on their personally selected avatar from five avatar body types according to their inputted information such as height and weight. If the shoppers like the garments, they can purchase the garments right there in the application. According to Raturi (2018), the user is required to bring the garment to the front of virtual mirror which scans the garment. After getting the information of the scanned garment, top of the user's body will be superimposed with the garment image. Then, the reflected image in the virtual mirror will display a virtual appearance of the user with the garment. Most importantly, the garment follows the body movements with totally real virtual movements.

III. AIM AND METHODOLOGY

A. The main objective of the proposed system is to enhance customer experience in clothing fitting by enabling customers to virtually try clothing on in order to check for size, fit or style.

1. To detect and extract human body skeleton-based joint positions using smartphone camera.

The human body detection system is developed to detect the body parts including head, lower and upper body with minimum latency. The system should be able to inform the user about successful or unsuccessful human body detection by displaying the detected body skeleton-based joints or error message respectively. In addition, the time needed for detection and extraction should be shorter compared to physically changing clothes or else this application does not make any contribution to time advantages for users.

2. To calculate body measurements based on the extracted body skeleton joint positions.

Body measurements are utilized to fit the virtual garments over human body in a more accurate way. The body measurements, including shoulder width, left and right arm length, left and right limb length can be obtained by calculating the distance between each of the body skeleton joint positions.

B. Methodology: Developing an AR virtual fitting room application using augmented reality and computer vision technologies for smartphones. Basically, the proposed application is built on Android mobile platform. Smartphone camera is the main requirement to detect, recognize and track human body movements in order to interact with the proposed application content such as virtual garment in real-time. The Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the application is designed as simple and easy to use in order to make it applicable to people in all age groups. The garment catalogue, garment details and camera preview are the necessary and main user interfaces in this application. The user interfaces must be designed and built based on the heuristic principles which are easy to learn, effective, easy to remember, error-free and pleasant to fulfil the usability criteria.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

As shown in Figure 2, the smartphone camera is used to detect and scan the user's body in order to obtain body skeleton joint position information and body measurements of the user. Then, the virtual garment is superimposed over the user's body by computing the data of body measurements, body skeleton joint position and garment measurements.

Figure.2 Flow diagram of system overview.

The virtual garment can be fitted seamlessly to the user's body for enhanced realism. Through the smartphone camera, the virtual garment follows the tracked user's body movements with real virtual movements in order to ensure that the virtual garment is fitted to the user's body. The virtual garment will be kept rendering in the real-world view according to the body

movements. In order to create and embed a customized camera in the application, android. hardware, camera2 package from Android, as known as Camera2 API is integrated and implemented to provide an interface to individual camera devices such as front and back camera which are connected to an Android device. Since it only supports Android API 21 and above, the minimum SDK version of the application is set to 21. In addition, the camera permission is declared in Android's manifest file to allow use of camera hardware and other related features.

By using this package, a camera device is modelled as a pipeline as shown in Figure3. It takes in requests for capturing a single frame as an input and capture single image based on each request. The requests are processed in-order and multiple requests are allowed to run asynchronously to maintain full framerate on Android device in order to reduce latency.

Figure.3 Camera Device's Model Pipeline Stage

In order to recognize, detect and track human body, pose estimation model for mobile by TensorFlow Lite is implemented to estimate the pose of a person in live video by estimating where body skeleton joint positions are. The joint positions detected which are indexed by "Part ID" has confidence score from 0.0 to 1.0. There are 14 joint positions detected including top, neck, right shoulder, right elbow, right wrist, left shoulder, left elbow, left wrist, right hip, right knee.

Figure. 3 Body skeleton joint positions

OpenCV library is downloaded and imported into the application as a module. Its native libraries are also imported into jniLibs folder to be integrated with the application. Some of the functions from OpenCV are used to read the frame and feed the image data into the model classifier to carry out pose estimation. Once the model and OpenCV libraries are loaded successfully, the image data is processed by Gaussian Blur to get enhanced image in order to increase classification accuracy. On the other hand, a set of heat maps is produced and generated to simultaneously capture features at a variety of scales. The heat maps predict the probability of the skeleton joints occurring at each pixel of the image. When the joint positions are successfully detected, the results will be returned from the classifier. For real-time view, the live video is passed to the model in frame by frame and then, the model returns the classification result back to the application.

Garment model must be customized to match with the skeleton joint positions since there's no apparel dataset which is suitable to be implemented. The garment model is generated based on actual garment with transparent background to provide accurate size and style to user in order to enhance the virtual clothing fitting experience.

Furthermore, the garment model is saved as Portable Network Graphics (PNG), a type of graphics file-format that supports lossless data compression. The reason to choose PNG format is because the data is preserved and there is no loss in data every time it is opened or saved. The most main advantage of PNG is it supports transparency compared to other graphics file-format such as Joint Photographic Experts Group (JPEG). In addition, Firebase Real-time Database is also utilized to store garment data including title, category, description and options of colours.

Superimposition of Garment Model over Human Body: Once the body skeleton joint positions are successfully detected, the virtual garment will be superimposed over the body based on the data of body measurements, body skeleton joint position and garment measurements. In order to do superimposition, garment model is converted into Bitmap class which is from android graphics. Bitmap package. Bitmap is used to create realistic graphic and image. Bitmap is a two-dimensional matrix composed of rectangular mesh of cells called pixels, each pixel containing a colour value as shown in *Figure*. They are characterized by two fundamental parameters which are the number of pixels and the information content as known as colour depth per pixel. Each pixel of the Bitmap will be handled and processed in custom way to match with the body skeleton joint points.

Figure.4 – Pixel description of Bitmap

Android. Graphics Matrix package from Android is integrated to perform scaling and transformation of the garment model to generate a matrix. The scaling of garment model is implemented based on the body measurements. The measurements are calculated based on the distances between each of the body skeleton joint positions as shown in Figure5. The body measurements include shoulder width, left and right arm length, left and right limb length.

Figure.5 Body measurements based on skeleton joint positions

The garment model is transformed frame by frame according to the body movement tracked in real-time. The offsets for transformation will be set according to the body skeleton joint points. Android Graphics Canvas package is utilized to draw the garment model onto the live video view based on the matrix generated with scaling and transformation parameters

System Architecture Design: The application is designed based on Model-View-Controller (MVC) architecture pattern as shown in Figure 6. MVC is a solid, established pattern that aims to isolate and separate the different aspects of an application into presentation and interaction. Each layer is responsible for an aspect of the app. According to MVC architecture pattern, there are 3 logical components that interact with each other which are Model, View and Controller.

Figure. 6 MVC architecture pattern

The Model component is the data layer, responsible for managing the application logic and data as well as handling associated operation on that data. Examples in this project are Firebase real-time database, OpenCV library and TensorFlow Lite model. View is the UI layer which defines and manages how the data from the Model is presented to the user data.

Controller is the logic layer, responsible for managing of the user’s behaviour and interaction such as item click event and updating the Model if needed. In this approach, every Activity and Fragment class in the application will act as Controller layer such as click listeners and item click listeners etc.

System Implementation: The methodology chosen to be applied in the development of AR virtual fitting room application is iterative model. Iterative model is a particular implementation of a software development life cycle (SDLC) that focuses on an initial, simplified implementation, which then progressively gains more complexity and a broader feature set until the final system is built entirely. It is an approach of breaking down the large software development process into smaller pieces. As shown in *Figure 7*, there are 6 main stages in iterative methodology: Requirement, Planning, Analysis and Design, Evaluation, Testing and Deployment. The reason to choose to apply iterative model in the development is because of its high flexibility compared to other methodologies. With the methodology, a part of the application can be implemented by starting with small sets of requirements in order to adapt the ever- changing scope and requirements with minimal losses in terms of time and cost. For additional requirements, functions are added or changed to meet the requirements in the next iteration in order to create a new version which is an improved version of previous iteration. Moreover, the application is easier to be tested and evaluated during an iteration in order to identify and manage risks. Any potential defects can be recognized quickly and reverted to previous iteration within a short time frame. Besides, blueprint and prototype of the application can be presented to users to acquire reliable feedback which is important in improving the application. In short, the scope and requirements that were previously set can be enhanced in order to help the developers to build and deliver a quality system quickly and easily with iterative model.

Figure.7 Iterative model

Verification and Validation: The AR virtual fitting room is developed to allow users to virtually try clothing on based on augmented reality and computer visioning. The system should be able to recognize and detect human body in order to obtain body skeleton joint positions and body measurements in most of the common condition types. The system should also be able to fit garment onto human body in real-time through smartphone camera. In order to verify the functionalities of the system, a few of tests in different situations are planned to be carried out after the system is developed. The verifications plans are shown in Table 1, Table 2, and Table 3.

1. Simple scene: A user is surrounded with simple and blank background. The system is required to detect user’s body skeleton joint position and fit garment onto user’s body in real-time.

Table1: Verification plan T1.

I. Procedure Number	II. T2
III. Method	IV. Testing
V. Applicable Requirements	VI. Detect user’s body skeleton joint position and fit garment onto user’s body in real-time.
VII. Purpose / Scope	VIII. To detect human body and fit garment onto human body in cluttered scene.
IX. Items Under Test	X. Live video
XI. Precautions	XII. The user should expose whole body to smartphone camera.
XIII. Special Conditions/Limitations	XIV. If the exposed human body is partial, the system may not be able to detect the human body accurately.

2. Cluttered Scene

A user is surrounded with other different types of objects. The system is required to detect user’s body skeleton joint position and fit garment onto user’s body in real-time.

Table 5.2 – Verification plan T2.

Procedure Number	T2
Method	Testing
Applicable Requirements	Detect user's body skeleton joint position and fit garment onto user's body in real-time.
Purpose / Scope	To detect human body and fit garment onto human body in cluttered scene.
Items Under Test	Live video
Precautions	The user should expose whole body to smartphone camera.
Special Conditions/Limitations	If the exposed human body is partial, the system may not be able to detect the human body accurately.

Black Box Testing: According to the features of application, risk level can be classified into 3 level:

low, medium, and high. Basically, high indicates that the effect of the risk for the feature would be very high and even non-tolerable. Medium risk level is tolerable but not desirable for the application although the risk is limited, while low risk level is tolerable. In order to prevent loss, feature with high risk level should be prioritized to test compared to the others. The following table (Table 5.3) contains the feature to be tested based on Section 3.3. Listed together are the feature ID and its corresponding descriptions, estimated risk level and test level.

Table 3: Features to be tested

Feature ID	Feature Description	Risk Level	Test Level
F001	Browse Garment Catalogue	High	System
F002	View Garment	High	System
F003	Capture Body Skeleton Joints	High	System
F004	Try Garment On	High	System
F005	Snap Photo	Medium	System

IV. CONCLUSION

The AR virtual fitting room application is designed to be lightweight and efficient that can be run on inexpensive hardware which is Android smartphone. Hence, users are allowed to experience AR and the body detection system by only installing the mobile application instead of whole system. In addition, the Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the application is simple and easy to use to make it applicable to people in all age groups. Users can get started with it quickly and easily. Basically, human body is detected, recognized, and tracked using smartphone camera in order to interact with the application content in real-time. Pose estimation is implemented to detect human body skeleton joint positions so that body movements can be tracked over the time. The body measurements can be obtained by calculating the distance between each of the skeleton joints detected. Then, the model of garment is fitted to the human body based on the body skeleton joint positions, body measurements as well as the garment measurements.

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